

DETERMINATION OF SOME QUALITY PARAMETERS OF WATER SAMPLES FROM NEW KUTUNKU, GWAGWALADA, ABUJA, NIGERIA

ABSTRACT

Ten water samples (NKT1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9 & 10) were collected from New Kutunku, Gwagwalada, Abuja, and analyzed for physical and chemical parameters. Parameters including Odour, taste, temperature, pH, electrical Conductivity, Acidity, Alkalinity, Total Dissolved Solids, total hardness, Chloride, Nitrates and sulphates were analyzed and are all in conform to the W.H.O standards for drinking water. The W.H.O standard shows that some of the samples are odourless and tasteless. The pH of water samples has a mean value of 6.95 that is in conformity with WHO standards value. Acidity in the water samples has a mean value of 0.122mg/l which is very low to the WHO standards. Total dissolved solids of water sample are low with a mean value of 4.43mg/l. Alkalinity in the water samples has a lower mean value of 20.15mg/l, which are lower than W.H.O standard. Nitrate has a mean value 0.64mg/l in the water samples which is lower compare to WHO standard. Also the mean values for total hardness (0.33mg/l), temperature (30°C), electrical conductivity (537.78mg/l), chloride (0.07mg/l) and sulphate (7.3mg/l) are all in conform to the W.H.O standards for drinking water.

Keywords: *drinking water, analysis, physiochemical, Gwagwalada.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Water which is a neutral oxide of hydrogen with formula H_2O is one of the most important Oxide known. It is abundant in the earth's crust. Its presence or otherwise is said to influence human settlement. The importance of water to living things cannot be overemphasised. It is believed to be the reason for life on planet Earth. Humans need water for various purposes, ranging from domestic to industrial uses. All living things depend on water for its existence (Hiremathet *al*, 2011; Parariya, 2012). Water being a universal solvent has many substances dissolved in it. These include those that are beneficial and those that are harmful to man. Its quality therefore depends on factors such as geological morphology, vegetation, land use and human activities such as domestic and industrial use of water. (Mishsraet *al*, 2013).

The availability of good quality water is an indispensable feature for preventing diseases and improving quality of life. Natural water contains some types of impurities whose nature and amount vary with source of water.

1.2 SOURCES OF WATER

Water naturally exists in three main sources; rain water, ground water and surface water.

Rain water is naturally the purest source of water but as it gets down it absorbs compounds from the atmosphere. Its main components are chlorides, nitrates, sulphates, sodium, potassium and ammonia. The rain can be collected from roofs and prepared water sheds which could assist in polluting and making it one of the most unfit sources of water for drinking (Huisman, *et al.*, 1981).

Groundwater is said to have emanated from the melting of meteoric water (rain, snow, and hailstone), into the ground, they have served as a source of domestic water supply. It offers a cheaper and purer supply. The main ionic components are chloride, nitrate, sulphates, potassium, sodium and calcium. This includes natural springs, wells and boreholes. Some level of purity is achieved on turbidity, colour, odour and taste. It reaches the surface through wells, shafts, springs, and boreholes. As it percolates into the earth it is subjected to some purification actions by the numerous chains of pervious and impervious rock strata or layers. Because of the disintegrating and dissolving power of water, it dissolves some of the rocks which make up the earth layers making it to have impurities like oxides, nitrate, sulphates, calcium, iron, magnesium (Kalua, & Chipeta, 2005).

Surface water includes streams, ponds and lakes, its main ionic compounds include chlorides, nitrates, sulphates, magnesium and calcium. The concentration of components here are more than those in rain water and ground water. Sea water could be considered as surface water. The salt content in it is so much that it cannot be used as drinking water because it would take the body a lot of work to flush out excess salt before usage for metabolism, it

is also inadequate in the machinery use as it rust machines, it kills most crops frequently carry suspended solids (Kirk et al., 1964)

1.3 IMPORTANCE OF WATER

Water plays an important role in the world economy in an area such as domestic, industrial, agricultural, contraction, and transportation.

Domestic uses of water include; cooking, washing of clothes, cars, dishes, showering, flushing away of wastes and drinking. The human body contains 55% to 78% water depending on body size (Lomborg, 2001). To function properly, the body requires between one and seven litres of water to avoid dehydration; the precise amount depends on the level of activity, temperature, humidity and other factors. Most of these are injected through foods or beverages other than drinking water directly. It is not clear how much water intake healthy people need, though most advocates agree that 6-7 of glasses of water daily is the minimum to maintain proper hydration (Linsey, et al., 1995). Water is used for fighting wildfires. Water has a high heat of vaporization and is relatively inert, which makes it a good fire-extinguishing fluid. The evaporation of water carries heat away from the fire.

In agriculture, the most important use of water is for irrigation, which is a key component to produce enough food. Irrigation takes up to 90% water withdrawn in some developing countries and significant proportions in developed countries, (United State 30% of freshwater usage is for irrigation (Niemi, et al., 1990).

Water is widely used in chemical reactions as a solvent, dissolving many ionic compounds. In organic reactions it does not dissolve the reactants well and is amphoteric (acidic and basic) and nucleophilic.

In recreation, water can be used for many purposes as well as for exercising and for sports. Some of these include swimming, boating, surfing and diving. In addition, some sports like ice hockey and ice skating are played on ice. Lake sides, beaches and water paths are popular place for people to go, relax and enjoy recreation. Humans also use water for snow sports like sledding, and snowboarding, which requires the water to be frozen.

Industrial uses of water includes; cooling of machinery in power plants, condenser cooling, sanitary services and for boilers. Many industrial processes rely on reactions using chemicals dissolved in water, suspensions of solids in water slurries or using water to dissolve and extract substances.

Water is used in power generation. Hydroelectricity is electricity obtained from hydropower. Hydroelectric power comes from water driving and a water turbine connected to a generator. Hydroelectricity is a low-cost, non-polluting, renewable energy source. The sun supplies the energy. Heat from the sun evaporates water, which condenses as rain at higher altitudes from where it flows down. Pressurized water is used in blasting and water jet cutters. Also,

very high-pressure water guns are used for precise cuttings. It works very well; it is relatively safe and not harmful to the environment. It is also used in the cooling of machinery to prevent overheating as in vehicle radiators.

1.4 AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The aim of this study is to determine the quality of some water samples from New Kutunku.

The objectives of this study are:

To determine odour, taste, temperature, electrical conductivity, pH, acidity, alkalinity total hardness chloride, total dissolved solids, nitrates and sulphates.

To compare the results with those from the literature and

To compare the parameter values to WHO standards.

To obtain baseline information for further study

2.0 MATERIALS,

2.1 APPARATUS AND EQUIPMENT

The apparatus and equipment's used for this experiment are: Spectrophotometer (210, VGP (buck)) Thermometer, Retort Stand, Conductivity Meter, Glass Electrode, pH Meter, Measuring Cylinder, Beakers (250 ml), Hot Plate, Conical Flasks, Burette, Pipette, Volumetric Flask, Test tube Racks, Spatula, Dropper, Glass Funnel, Evaporating Dish, Sterile plastic Bottles (1 Litre) , Oven, Weighing balance, Tissue Papers.

2.2 CHEMICALS AND REAGENTS

The chemicals and reagents used for this study are: Distilled water, Hydrochloric acid, Potassium dichromate

Eriochrome black T indicator, Methyl orange indicator, Ammonia buffer solution, Potassium chromate indicator, Phenolphthalein, Sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) (0.02M), Silver nitrate ($AgNO_3$) (0.01M), Disodium ethylenediaminetetraacetate (Na_2EDTA) (0.01M), Sodium hydroxide (0.01M), Pillow powder, Methyl orange indicator, Phenolphthalein indicator, Sodium hydroxide ($NaOH$) (0.02M) Ammonia buffer solution, Silver nitrate ($AgNO_3$) (0.1M), pH 4 and pH 7.

2.3 SAMPLING

2.3.1 DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

The area of this study is New Kutunku situated at Gwagwalada area council, Abuja, Nigeria. New Kutunku is a congested populated area. It serves both residential and commercial purposes. New Kutunku has poor sanitary conditions as a result of the presence of Gwagwalada market, abattoir and ongoing construction projects. The major inhabitants are the indigenes who basically sell their goods in the market and some students and workers who live around the area.

The samples were collected from Kutunku River, tap water closed to the abattoir compound, tap water from Mr Usman and Uche compound, well water from madam Bisi, Mr. Robert, mummy Rose, and Mr. Kola compounds.

Samples such as ones collected from rivers and some wells are by mere looking have to undergo much purification due to human and animal activities within the area such as: dumping of refuses, rearing of animals by herdsman, agricultural activities and pollutants from construction.

The samples collected were labelled as NKT1, NKT2, NKT3, NKT4, NKT5, NKT6, NKT7, NKT8, NKT9 and NKT10.

2.3.2 SAMPLE COLLECTION

Each water sample was collected using 1L rubber bottle. Samples NKT1 and NKT2 were collected from Kutunku River by dipping the 1L bottle inside the river. Samples NKT3, NKT4 and NKT5 were collected from tap which was opened and allowed to run for some minutes before collection into the 1L bottles from Abattoir and Mr Usman compound. Sample NKT6, NKT7, NKT8, NKT9 and NKT10 were fetched from well from Mr Uche, Madam Bisi, Mr. Robert, Mummy Rose and Mr. Kola compound. The temperature of the sample was taken using a thermometer at the site of collection and samples were then taken to laboratory for analysis.

2.4 ANALYSIS

2.4.1 DETERMINATION OF ODOUR

50ml of the sample was measured into a 250ml beaker. It was shaken for some seconds and immediately the odour was observed by putting the nostrils near the mouth of the beaker. The observations were then recorded for each sample.

2.4.2 DETERMINATION OF TASTE

The taste of the water sample was determined by tasting. Since the degrees of perception of the intensities of the taste vary from one person to another.

2.4.3 DETERMINATION OF TEMPERATURE

The thermometer was rinsed with distilled water and cleaned with tissue paper. 250ml beaker was filled with 100ml of the sample. Then the thermometer was inserted into it, the value of the temperature was recorded. The thermometer was rinsed with distilled water and cleaned with tissue paper before it was used for other samples.

2.4.4 DETERMINATION OF ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY

The conductivity meter was calibrated. The electrode was wetted thoroughly and then plugged into the conductivity meter. Then it was inserted in to a 250ml beaker containing distilled water. The conductivity meter was then switched on, and zero error was corrected. The distilled water was replaced with water samples(100ml) and the electrode was inserted in each case. The system was allowed to stabilize and the reading was recorded.

2.4.5 DETERMINATION OF pH

The pH meter was calibrated. The glass electrode was thoroughly wetted with distilled water. This was done by connecting glass electrode to the pH meter and inserting the electrode into the buffer solution. It was allowed to stabilize and pH meter reading indicated 4.0, which is equal to its known value. The same thing was repeated using buffer solution with pH of 7.0. The beaker containing buffer solution was then replaced consecutively with the ones containing water samples (100ml) and the electrode was inserted into it. This was then allowed to stabilize and the readings were recorded.

2.4.6 DETERMINATION OF TOTAL DISSOLVED SOLIDS

Ten washed 100ml beakers were dried and then put in an oven for a while, cooled and the weight of each of the 100ml beakers was taken which became the initial weight. 50ml of each of the water samples was transferred into each of the 100ml beakers and weighed. This was then placed on a hot plate, and heated until the water was completely dried. The beaker was allowed to cool and weighed giving the final weight.

The total dissolved solids was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Total dissolved solids (mg/L)} = \frac{(\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial weight}) \times 1000}{\text{Volume of water used}}$$

2.4.7 DETERMINATION OF TOTAL HARDNESS

100ml of each water samples was transferred into a clean 250ml conical flask. 2ml of ammonia buffer solution was added and 3 drops of Eriochrome Black T indicator were also added. The mixture was titrated against 0.01M Na₂EDTA solution. At the end point the colour changed was from pink to blue. The volume of Na₂EDTA solution used was recorded.

The total hardness was calculated using the following formular:

$$\text{Total hardness (mg/L)} = \frac{\text{titre value} \times \text{morality of Na}_2\text{EDTA} \times 1000}{\text{Volume of sample}}$$

2.4.8 DETERMINATION OF ACIDITY

100ml of each water samples were measured into 250ml conical flasks. 0.02M NaOH solution was filled in the burette. To the water sample in the 250ml conical flask, 2 drops of phenolphthalein indicator was added to each. The mixture was titrated with 0.02M NaOH. At the end point the colour changed from colourless to pink showing phenolphthalein acidity.

The acidity was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Acidity (mg/L)} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times 0.02 \times 100 \times 1000}{\text{Volume of sample}}$$

2.4.9 ALKALINITY

100ml of each water samples was measured into 250ml conical flask. 3 drops of phenolphthalein were added to each sample. There was no colour change. Then 3 drops of methyl orange were added and then titrated against 0.01M H₂SO₄. Until the colour changed from yellow to orange, the titre values were recorded.

The alkalinity was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Alkalinity (mg/L)} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times 0.01 \times 1000}{\text{Volume of sample}}$$

2.4.10 DETERMINATION OF CHLORIDES

50ml of each sample was transferred into the 250ml conical flask. 3 drops of potassium dichromate indicator were added. This mixture was titrated against 0.01M AgNO₃. At the end point the colour changed was from yellow to a tinge of brown. The titre values were recorded.

The chloride was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Chlorides (mg/L)} = \frac{\text{titre value} \times 0.01 \text{ (N AgNO}_3 \text{ solution)} \times 1000}{\text{Volume of sample}}$$

2.4.11 DETERMINATION OF NITRATES

The spectrophotometer was calibrated. 10ml of the samples was measured into 250ml conical flasks. The pillow was cut opened and poured into each flask. It was allowed to dissolve for some minutes. The wavelength '353' was entered into the spectrophotometer. The sample cell was filled with distilled water and was used as the blank sample. The 'ZERO' key was pressed. The sample was then transferred into the sample cells and placed in the spectrophotometer. The 'READ' key was pressed and the value displayed on the screen was recorded.

2.4.12 DETERMINATION OF SULPHATES

The spectrophotometer was calibrated. 10ml of each sample was transferred into their 250ml conical flasks. The pillow for sulphate test was opened and the contents transferred into the samples in the 250ml conical flasks. The mixture was allowed to dissolve. The wavelength '680' was entered into the spectrophotometer. The sample cell was filled with distilled water and placed as the blank sample. The 'ZERO' key was pressed. The sample was transferred into the sample cells and placed in the spectrophotometer. The 'READ' key was pressed and the value displayed on the screen was recorded.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 RESULTS

The results of this study are presented in Table 3.2 based on the chemical and physical analysis carried out on the samples and was compared to table 3.1 of the World Health Organization guidelines for safe drinking water (2004)

Table 3.1: World Health Organization guidelines for safe drinking water (2004)

PARAMETERS	PERMISSIBLE LIMIT
Odour	Unobjectionable/odourless
Taste	Unobjectionable/tasteless
Temperature	30°C
pH	6.5 – 8.5
Conductivity	1000µs/cm
Turbidity	5NTU
Total dissolved solids	1500mg/l
Alkalinity	100mg/l
Hardness	500mg/l
Nitrates(NO ₃ ²⁻)	50mg/l
Sulphates (SO ₄ ²⁻)	200mg/l

Table 3.2: results of the analysis

SAMPLES	NK T1	NK T2	NK T3	NK T4	NK T5	NK T6	NK T7	NK T8	NK T9	NK T10	MEAN VALUES	WHO (2004) RANGE
PARAMETERS												
Odour	Objectionable	Objectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Objectionable	Objectionable	Objectionable	Objectionable	Objectionable	Objectionable	Objectionable
Taste	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable										
Temperature (°C)	30	30	27	28	27	29	30	30	29	29	28.9	30
Electrical conductivity (Us/cm)	464	395	94,6	96.3	88.9	79.1	823	743	952	895	537.78	1000

pH	6.76	6.63	6.83	6.77	6.76	6.53	7.34	7.70	7.21	7.01	6.95	6.5-8.0
Acidity (Mg/L)	0.24	0.26	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.06	0.24	0.2	0.1	0.18	0.122	6-8.5
Alkalinity (Mg/L)	1.78	18.2	0.2	0.3	0.26	1.18	3.4	3.02	4.1	5.3	20.154	100
Total hardness (Mg/L)	0.38	0.35	0.53	0.49	0.45	0.19	0.12	0.25	0.28	0.22	0.326	500
Chloride (Mg/L)	0.1	0.1	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.13	0.13	0.02	0.13	0.09	0.078	250
Total dissolved solids (Mg/L)	5.0	5.3	3.8	3.5	4.1	4.2	4.0	4.5	4.8	5.1	4.43	1500
Nitrate (Mg/L)	0.3	0.3	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.8	0.9	0.8	1.0	0.9	0.64	50
Sulphate (Mg/L)	6	6	9	9	8	7	7	7	7	7	7.3	200

3.2 DISCUSSION

3.2.1 Odour and Taste

According to the results in table 4.1 above, some of the water samples (NKT1, NKT2, NKT6, NKT7, NKT8 NKT9 and NKT10) are objectionable due to presence of dirty refuses, living microscopic organisms or decaying organic matter including weeds, algae or industrial wastes containing ammonia, phenols, halogen, hydrocarbons. It is evident from the Tables that the water samples possess some perceived odour that was not within the range of WHO (2004).

Also from Table 4.1.1 above, some of the water samples (NKT3, NKT4 and NKT) are Unobjectionable and is in conformity with WHO standards (2004). These water points have often been subjected to such treatments to mitigate any potential health hazards. In practice, in the great majority of cases, taste is assessed by an individual analyst and is described subjectively. Thus taste of a water sample objectionable to one person may not be to another (WHO 1993).

3.2.2 Temperature

The temperature of the samples ranged from 27.0 to 30°C (Table 4.1). The relatively low sampling temperature could be attributed to the fact that most of the samples were collected very early in the morning. According to WHO guidelines, 30°C is the recommended limit. Based on those guidelines, the temperature of the samples does not pose any threat to the consumers. Temperature of drinking water is often not a major concern to consumers especially in terms of drinking water quality. The quality of water with respect to temperature is usually left to the individual taste and preference and there are no set guidelines for drinking water temperature.(DWAF, 1995)

This is so as it is known that New Kutunku, Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja FCT, is located in the Sudan Savannah region of the country with temperature rising to as high as 33°C during the dry seasons. The period at which this study was carried out was the period of transition from dry to rainy season. Also, the results were influenced by the climatic nature of the area, low rainfall, topography and soil structure which cannot support luxuriant vegetation which would have provided good soil cover from the direct way of the sun as found in the Southern part of the country. From this report, we can deduce that temperature within this range will reduce the solubility of oxygen and amplify odour due to anaerobic reaction (DWAF; 1995).

Test for temperature does not carry much significance because there is no treatment which can be impacted to control the temperature in any water supply project (Brain C.I, Zeugen N.S; 1996).

3.2.3 Electrical Conductivity

Electrical conductivity values varied from 89.9 to 952 μ s/cm. The acceptable limit of conductivity is 1500 μ s/cm (WHO, 1992). Electrical conductivity values fall within the acceptable limit prescribed by WHO limits.

Generally, conductivity of clean water is lower but as it moves down the earth it leaches and dissolves ions from the soil and also picks up organic from biota and detritus (Ferrar, 1989).

Electrical conductivity gives an account of all the dissolved ions in solution. High conductivity may lead to lowering the aesthetic value of the water by giving mineral taste to the water. For the industrial and agricultural activity, conductivity of water is critical to monitor. Water with high conductivity may cause corrosion of metal surface of equipment such as boiler. It is also applicable to home appliances such as water heater system and faucets (Katsoyiannis *et al.*, 2013).

3.2.4 pH

The pH range does vary significantly in the various samples. For all the New Kutunku samples, the pH range from 6.53 to 7.70 which fall within the WHO limits for standard drinking water. An acceptable pH range for drinking water is 6.5-8.5; therefore the water samples are fit for drinking. Hence the pH values of the different water samples analysis are in accordance with the W.H.O standard.

Water is considered to be acidic if the pH is below 7.0. Meanwhile, it is alkaline if the pH is higher than 7.0. Acidic water can lead to corrosion of metal pipes and plumping system. Meanwhile, alkaline water shows disinfection in water. (Meybeck, 1997).

3.2.5 Acidity

The acidity in all the collected water samples is in the range of 0.06 mg/L to 0.26 mg/L. The Acidity of the water samples collected from different sources in New Kutunku Gwagwalada Abuja, were found to be within the recommended limits of WHO.

3.2.6 Alkalinity

The values of total alkalinity in the samples range between 0.2 mg/l to 5.3 mg/l which falls within the prescribed limits recommended for drinking water.

Alkalinity is the measure of the capacity of water sample to react with a strong acid usually H₂SO₄ to a predetermined value. It does not refer to pH but instead refers to the ability of water to resist change in pH value. This is due to the presence of bicarbonates, carbonates and hydroxides compounds of sodium,

calcium and potassium. It is determined by titrating water samples with standard solution of strong acids. Alkalinity itself is not harmful to human beings (Malviya, et al., 2010).

3.2.7 Total Hardness

Total hardness value in the water sample from New Kutunku is within the range of 0.12 mg/l to 0.53 mg/l which is within the range of WHO standard which shows no significance difference. The United States Public Health Service recommends a maximum of 500 mg/l hardness in drinking water (USGS, 2012).

Hardness of water may not have any health implications but may affect the taste of water as well as influence its lathering ability when used for washing. This depends on the amount of Calcium and Magnesium salts (Singh, 2010).

3.2.8 Chloride

The chloride content of the water samples ranged from 0.09 to 0.13 mg/l. The WHO standard for chloride in drinking water is 250 mg/l and the samples were all within the acceptable limits prescribed by WHO. Chlorine is an active chemical which has disinfecting capabilities. The sources of chlorine in natural water may be from mine drainage waste and from dissolving rocks. The closeness of the water source to the sea can also influence the chloride content since the sea is characteristically saline. Chloride in water may react with sodium to form sodium chloride. Since sodium chloride has the salty taste, it can be deduced that Chloride in water impacts a salty taste in the water. However the salty taste may be absent in water containing as high as 1000 mg/l chlorine when the predominant cations are calcium and magnesium. That is to say that too much of chlorine in water makes the water esthetically undesirable for drinking purposes. Chloride concentration in excess of about 250 mg/l can give rise to a detectable taste in water (Lockhart et al 1955).

3.2.9 Total Dissolved solids

The value for total dissolved solids ranged from 3.5 to 5.3 mg/L. These values were within the WHO standard value of 1000.00.

McCutcheon (1983) stated that the palatability of water with total dissolved solids level less than 600 Mg⁻¹ is generally considered to be good whereas water with total dissolved solids greater than 1200 mg/l becomes increasingly unpalatable.

Theoretically, dissolved solids are the anhydrous residues of the dissolved substances in water samples. It is related to both conductivity and turbidity (APHA: 1998).

3.2.10 Nitrates

Nitrate content of the water sample ranged from 0.3 to 1.0 mg/l conforming to the WHO standard are suitable for drinking. Nitrogen is present in soils which are normally fixed by nitrogen-fixing bacteria. Nitrogen may exist as nitrates and nitrites. Nitrogen like any other nutrient is harmless in lower concentrations but becomes harmful only in higher interconvertible organic nitrogen.

3.2.11 Sulphates

The sulphate of the water samples ranged from 6.0 to 9.0 mg/l and were within the WHO limit of 250 mg/l. Sulphate gets into groundwater through the dissolution of rocks containing sulphur and mine drainage waste. Water with sulphate levels above 500 mg/l can have a laxative effect until an adjustment to the water is made. The effect of sulphate depends largely on the body mass of an animal - the smaller the animal, the greater the effect. Increased sulphate levels can cause deficiencies in trace minerals which can contribute to a depressed growth rate and infertility in herd. The most serious is thiamine deficiency. The major physiological effect resulting from the ingestion of large quantities of sulphate leads to catharsis, dehydration, and gastrointestinal irritation. Water containing magnesium sulphate at levels above 600 mg/l acts as a purgative in humans. The presence of sulphate in drinking water can also result in a noticeable taste, the lowest taste threshold concentration for sulphate. (WHO, 1993)

4.0 CONCLUSION

It is reveal from the results from table 4.1, that the concentration levels for the physical and chemical parameters (odour, taste, temperature, electrical conductivity, pH, total dissolved solids, alkalinity, acidity, total hardness, chloride, nitrate and sulphate) do not exceed the maximum world health organization permissible limits. It can therefore be concluded that the some water samples collected from New Kutunku are substantially polluted due to various pollutants examples like samples collected from Kutunku River (NKT1 & NKT2) and wells. Therefore, this water cannot be used for any domestic or industrial purposes. Several adverse effects may be cause by the polluted water on the health & hygiene of the people staying in area. Therefore a mechanism for continuous monitoring of the quality of the water in New Kutunku is required. Also concentrated efforts are required from all concerned to reduce dumping of industrial and residential wastes in the river waters. According to WHO, nearly 80% of all the diseases in human beings are caused by water. Hence, the quality and health implications of drinking water are usually of interest.

5.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results obtained, we arrived to the following recommendations

It is recommended that water quality analysis should be carried out on all the samples, at least once every two years. This will ensure that incidences of contamination are noticed earlier for remedial action to be taken.

The communities should be educated on the need to keep their surroundings clean.

Chlorination process should be embarked upon to eliminate negative impacts of water contamination. Covering the wells immediately after chlorination would also enhance the water quality.

Pit or latrine toilet systems should be discouraged particularly in houses close to these water points. Seepages from sewages and soak-away in neighbouring houses to these water points should be checked and corrected.

Fast urbanization, extensive agricultural and aquaculture farming and intensive resulting in discharge of untreated or partially treated wastewater, coupled with a massive exploitation of water for irrigation, industrial and domestic use, are the main causes of water quality degradation.

As supply of safe water was made as a right, it is recommended that water sources need to be checked at regular intervals to monitor its quality and water should be treated before use for drinking purposes.

The drainage and septic tanks must be constructed far away from the wells taps and rivers

Generally, water pipelines and septic pipe lines of the town run parallel to each other thereby giving chances for contamination of drinking water.

Enough care should be taken by municipal authorities to separate these lines to prevent faecal contamination. Faecal contamination may takes place because of open defecation practices, running of water pipes close to sewage lines, developing of negative pressure and intermittent supply of water. Therefore, continues water supply is recommended.

Open air defecation along the canal bunds should be banned.

Good sanitation practices should be implemented near open well and tap water sources.

Regularly Physiochemical and microbiological tests should be carried out so as to protect the public from waterborne disease outbreaks.

REFERENCES

- Ahearn, D.S., Sheibley, R.W., Dahlgren, R.A., Anderson, M., Johnson, J., Tate K.W., (2005). Land use and land cover influence on water quality in the last free-flowing river draining the western Sierra Nevada, California. *J. of Hydrology* 313, Issues 3-4, 234-247
- APHA, (1992). Standard methods for analysis of water and wastewater. 18th Ed. American Public Health Association, Inc., Washington D C.
- APHA (1998); *Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater*; American Public Health Association, Washington D.C
- APHA (1985): Standard Methods For Examination of Water and Wastewater, 20th Edition, American Public Health Association, Washington D. C.
- Brain C.I, Zeugen N.S; (1996); *Water Quality Monitoring and Environmental Status in Nigeria*; F.E.P.A Monograph 6; F.E.P.A Abuja, Nigeria; p 239
- Chandra S., Singh A. and Tomar P. K. (2012) "Assessment of Water Quality Values in Porur Lake Chennai, HussainSagar Hyderabad and Vihar Lake Mumbai, India", *ChemSci Trans.*, 1(3), 508-515.
- DWAF; (1995); *South African Water Quality Management Series; Procedure to Access Effluent Discharge Impacts*; WRC Reports No TT64194; Department of Water Affairs and Forestry Research Commission; Pretoria; pp 510
- Ferrar A. A. (1989). Ecological Flow Requirements for South African Rivers. South African National Scientific Programmes, Report No. 162.).
- Gaikwad R. W., Sasane V. V, (2013) "Assessment of ground water quality in and around Lonar lake and possible water treatment", *International Journal of Environmental Sciences*, Volume 3, No 4.
- Garg VK, Chaudhary A, Deepshikha, Dahiya S, (1999). An appraisal of groundwater quality in some village of district Jind. *Indian J Environ Prot*, 19(4), 267-272
- Grabow, W.O.K. (2000). The Safety of Water Disinfection Chem.andMicrob. Risks. Radisson Denville Resort, Miami Beach, Florida. USA, 15-17 November.
- Gurcharam S.A (1990); *Water Supply and Sanitary Engineering*; FAO; Rome; pp 47-140, 142-176, 420-422.
- Harnova R. K. (2003). Nutrient Variation in the Urban Drainage water of Harare, Zimbabwe; assessment of regularity aspects, Diffuse Pollution, Dublin.

- Hart, C.A.(2000). *Escherichia coli* and diarrhoea disease. *Postgraduate Doctor Africa*. 24(2):32-36.
- Hiremath, S. C. Yadawe, M. S., Pujeri, U. S., Hiremath, D. M. and Pujar, A. S. (2011).Physicochemical Analysis of Ground Water in Municipal Area of Bijapur (Karnataka).*Curr. World Environ*. 6 (2) 265 – 269.
- Huisman, L., & Wood, E. (1981).*Technology of small water supply system*. England: Hofkes E.H ed. p 8.
- Islam M. S., Ismail B. S., Barzani G. M., Sahibin A. R. and Ekhwan T. M. (2012) "Hydrological Assessment and Water Quality Characteristics of Chini Lake, Pahang, Malaysia", *American- Eurasian J. Agric. & Environ. Sci.*, 12 (6): 737- 749.
- Kalua, P.W.R., &Chipeta, W.P.C. (2005).*A situation analysis of water sector in Malawi*. In a paper presented at the workshop on situation analysis of water sector in Malawi, September 2005.
- Katsoyiannis and A. I. Zouboulis, 2013. "Removal of uranium from contaminated drinking water: a mini review of available treatment methods," *Desalination and Water Treatment*, vol. 51, no. 13–15, pp. 2915–2925)
- Kirk, T. (2nded.). (1964). *Encyclopaedia of chemical technology*. New York: John Wiley and Sons. pp. 66-90.
- Kirkwood, A. (1998). Safe Water for Africa. *Africa Health* 20(6):9 10.
- Kushreshtha, S.I.N. (1998). A global outlook for water resources to the year 2025. *Water resources management*.New York: Academic Press Inc.12 (1), 1-18.
- Lockhart EE, Tucker CL, Merrit MC (1955); *The Effect of Water Impurities on the Flavour of Brewed Coffee*; *Food Research*, 1955 20:598
- Lomborg, B. (2001). *The skeptical environmentalist*.Massachusetts: Cambridge University Press.
- Linsey, R.K., Franzin, J.B., Freyberg, D.L., &Tchobaroglons, G. (4thed.). (1995). *Water resources engineering*. London: Sowy .J. Publishers. pp. 34-45.
- Leonard L.C. 1971. *Water and Water Pollution Vol 1*, Marcel Dekkar Inc., New York
- MacCutheon, S. C., Martin, J. l. and Barnwell, Jr. T. O. (1983). *Water quality*.In hand of hydrology. McGraw-Hill Inc. New York.
- Malviya, S.K. Diwakar, S.O.N. Choubey (2010); *Orient.J.Chem*.26(1): 319-323

- Macan, J.E. (1958), *Organic Chemistry* (3rd ed.), Belmont: Wadsworth,
- Mahesh M. K., Sushmitha B. R., Uma H. R. (2013) "Assessment of Water Quality for Hebbal Lake of Mysore", ISSN No. 2277 - 8160, Volume: 2.
- Meitei N.S. and P.M. Patil, (2004). Water Quality of Purna River in Puma town in Maharashtra, *Journal of Aqua Biology* 19, 77- 78
- Meybeck M, Rev. Geol. Dyn. Geogr. Phys., (1997), 21, 215-246 In article
- Mishra, M. K. Mishra N. and Pandey, S. N. (2013).An assessment of the Physiocochemical Characteristics of Bhanka Pond, Hanumana, Rewa District India.*Intl.J. of Innov.Res.in Sci. Eng. and Techn.* 2 (5) 1781 – 1788
- Nagarsekar, A. S. and Kakde, U.B, (2014). A Study of Physico- Chemical Parameters of MithiRiver Water In Mumbai Metropolis. *International Research Journal of Chemistry* (IRJC), 5: 24-42
- Niemi, G.J., Devore, P., Detenbeck, N., Taylor, D., & Lima, A. (1990). *Overview of case studies on recovery of aquatic systems form disturbance*. Environment management. New Jersey: Brown and Co. Publishers. pp.571-587.
- Panda, R.B., Sahu, B.K., Sinha, B.K. and Nayak A. A. (1991). comparative study and diurnal variation of Physiochemical Characteristics of River, Well and Pond Water at Rourkela Industrial Complex of Orissa, *J. Ecotoxicol Environment monitoring* (3) 206-217.
- Parariya, S. K..(2012). Analysis of Water Quality Using Physico-Chemical Parameters of Kolura Pond in Post Monsoon Season, October, 2012.*Intl J. Chem. Phy. Sci.* 1 (2):48 – 53.
- Pradhan V., Mohsin M., Gaikwad B. H. (2012)"Assessment of physico chemical parameters of Chilika Lake water", *International Journal of Research in Environmental Science and Technology*, 2(4): 101-103.
- Puri P. J., Yenkie M. K. N., Sangal S. P., Gandhare N. V., Sarote G. B. and Dhanorkar D. B. (2011) "Surface water (Lakes) quality assessment in Nagpur city (India) based on Water quality index (WQI)", Vol.4, No.1, 43-48.
- Ramesh Janjala and M.M. Vaishnav, (2012).Physico-chemical monitoring and statistical evaluation of surface water in Korba District, C.G. India. *Indian Journal of Environmental Sciences* Vol.16, No.1(2012).
- Reid, P.C..Rickard, C.E.F, White, A.H. and Chem. J. (1985).Soc.,Dalton Trans. 753.

- Sahu.B.K. (1991). A study of aquatic pollution load in the River Brahmani
PhD thesis, SambalpurUniversity.
- Sheikh V. B. Y., Bhosale P. R., Nagargoje, B. N. (2013) "Water Quality Assessment of Nagzari Dam of Maharashtra." *Journal of Applied Technology in Environmental Sanitation*, Volume 3, Number 3: 111-116.
- ShresthaS, and Kazama F (2007). Assessment of surface waterquality using multivariate statistical techniques: a case study of Fuji river basin, Japan. *Environ. Model.Soft.* 22(4): 464-475
- Singh, B., Khurana S.C., Manish K., Tadav N., and Yadav R. (2012). Seasonal Variation of Coliforms and Nitrate in Groundwater Quality in Kanpur Metro. India. *International Journal of Research in Chemistry and Environment* Vol. 2 Issue 2 April 2012(207-209) ISSN 2248- 964
- Singh, M. R., Gupta A..andBeateswari, K. H.(2010)Physico chemical Properties of Water Samples for Manipur River System India. *J. Appl. Sci. Environ. Manage (JASEM)* 14(4): 85 89
- Simpi B, Hiremath SM, Murthy KNS (2011). Analysis of Water Quality Using Physico-Chemical Parameters HosahalliTank in Shimoga District, Karnataka, India, *Global Journal of Science Frontier Research*,11:(3).
- Slipigun, P., & Von, Z. (2nded.) . (1991). *Ion chromatography ofwater analysis in context.* USA: Mc Graw Hill Books Company. pp. 121-122.
- Taylor, E.W., & Green, N.P. (3rded.). (1992). *Biological science.*New Jersey: Brown and Co. Publishers. pp. 25-28.
- Taylor, E.W. (7thed.). (1958). *Examination of water and water suppliers.*New Jersey:Brown and Co. Publishers. Pp. 12-15.
- Thompson, T. and Khan, S. (2003). Situation analysis and epidemiology of infectious disease transmission: a South-Asian regional perspective. *International Journal of Environmental Health Research*, 13: S29-S39.
- UNEP, (2000). State of the Environment (SOE): overview at regional and global levels. *Environmental outlook (GEO)*, Vol. 2 Washington, DC.
- United State Geological Survey (USGS), (2012). <http://www.usgs.gov>, 08/06/2012 11:45AM.)
- USEPA (2004); *Drinking Water Treatment*; AWWA Drinking Water Week Blue Thumb Kit; www.epa.gov/safewater; EPA 816F04034
- WHO/UNICEF, (2000).Global Water Supply and Sanitation Assessment Report. Geneva, World Health Organisation. ISBN 94 4156201.

- World Health Organisation (WHO), (1992).Guidelines for drinking-water quality. Vol. 1 Geneva, Pp. 145-196.)
- WHO, (2002).Managing Water in the Home: Accelerated Health Gains from Improved Water Supply. Geneva: World Health Organisation, Document No. WHO/SDE/WDE/WSH/02.Available:<http://www.who.int/phe>.
- W.H.O. (1984). *Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality, Drinking water quality control in small community supplies*. WHO, Geneva, Switzerland 3: 121-130.
- WHO (World Health Organisation).(1993). Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality.2nd Edition.World Health Organisation, Geneva, Switzerland. In article
- World Health Organisation (WHO), (2004).Guidelines for drinking-water quality 3rd Ed. Vol. 1 Geneva Pp. 145-196.